

Dilemmas and Paths in the Application of Red Resources in University Students' Ideological and Political Education

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Abstract

Red resources represent the sum of valuable spiritual wealth and material carriers collectively created by the Chinese Communist Party and the people of all ethnic groups under its leadership through their great practice of revolution, construction, and reform. The noble spiritual connotations and scientific theoretical qualities of red resources, along with the special status of university students, necessitate the application of red resources in university students' ideological and political education, transforming them into quality educational resources. However, the characteristics of economic globalization and multicultural era, as well as the uniqueness of red resources themselves, have created certain difficulties in this transformation process. Currently, we should actively explore effective paths to organically apply red resources in university students' ideological and political education, fully utilizing their educational functions to continuously enhance the targeting and effectiveness of university students' ideological and political education.

Keywords: *Red Resources, University Students, Ideological and Political Education.*

1. Introduction

Red resources are the valuable spiritual wealth and material carriers accumulated by the Chinese Communist Party and the Chinese people under its leadership during the great practice of revolution, construction, and reform. They not only embody profound historical and cultural connotations but also possess important educational functions. They centrally demonstrate the revolutionary spirit of selfless dedication, solid and rigorous thinking style, and noble excellent traditions of Chinese Communists, carrying the Party's practical wisdom and cultural inheritance. As an important component of ideological and political education in universities, the revolutionary spirit, national integrity, and noble morality of red resources can help university students strengthen their ideals and beliefs, shape correct worldviews, outlooks on life, and values, and cultivate their patriotic sentiments and sense of social responsibility. Against the backdrop of intertwined multicultural and diversified values, the spiritual leadership role of red resources becomes increasingly prominent. Therefore, how to scientifically and rationally transform red resources into educational resources that are easily accepted and internalized by university students has become one of the core issues in university ideological and political education.

However, the effective application of red resources faces many practical challenges. The passage of time has created a sense of distance between red resources and contemporary university students' actual lives, dispersed resource distribution increases acquisition difficulty, theoretical abstraction depth poses high demands on university students' comprehension abilities, and psychological barriers further weaken the appeal of red resources. Meanwhile, contemporary university students' thinking characteristics show stronger independence, diversity, and criticality. Coupled with the rapid development of the information age and the impact of cultural values, the dissemination of red resources has become more complex. Against this background, university ideological and political education needs to explore deeply from both theoretical and practical levels. By excavating the ideological connotations of red resources and their alignment with ideological and political education goals, and innovating educational methods and communication carriers, red resources can better meet university students' needs and psychological characteristics. Universities should

scientifically plan and implement comprehensive measures to maximize the important role of red resources in ideological guidance and value orientation, thereby enhancing the targeting and effectiveness of university students' ideological and political education.

2 The Inevitability of Applying Red Resources in University Students' Ideological and Political Education and Transforming Them into Educational Resources

2.1 High Alignment Between Red Resources and Ideological and Political Education Goals and Value Pursuits

"Ideological and political education is a process of shaping university students' emotional attitudes and worldview, outlook on life, and values. It encompasses education requirements for students' thoughts, morals, concepts, psychology, consciousness, and value judgments (Li & Liu, 2011)". Ideological and political education is essentially a "soul-casting project" education, helping university students establish correct worldviews, epistemology, and values, enabling them to possess lofty ideals and beliefs. Red resources contain profound historical implications and far-reaching value culture, inherently permeated with Marxist scientific guiding ideology, excellent traditional Chinese culture, and great national spirit. Their profound ideological connotations, advanced cultural concepts, and noble spiritual values reflect the revolutionary spirit, thinking style, and excellent qualities of Chinese Communists and the People's Army, highlighting the revolutionary nature and advancement of Chinese revolutionary theory, embodying the subject status and pioneering spirit of the masses, and demonstrating the flesh-and-blood connection and deep bond between the Party and the masses. Whether in revolutionary war years or construction development and reform innovation periods, red resources' ideological and political education has always taken the comprehensive development of humans and society as its mission, serving as an important ideological source guiding university students to pursue positive and correct life value goals. These contents have always been emphasized and adhered to in ideological and political education, having strong practical significance for university ideological and political education work. The value pursuit embodied in red resources highly aligns with the goals and connotations of contemporary ideological and political education's values and interest education, representing the eternal value pursuit of ideological and political education practice activities, thus becoming an important content of ideological and political education (Li, 2013). Therefore, university students' ideological and political education cannot be separated from red resources, and we should fully interpret and explore the value implications of red resources, providing new perspectives for university students' ideological and political education, maximizing their educational functions.

2.2 The Special Status of University Students

Looking back at various historical periods of China's revolution, construction, and reform, our Party has always highly valued, cared for, and trusted young people, placing high hopes on them and dedicating itself to cultivating them as "qualified builders and reliable successors of the socialist cause". When Mao Zedong visited the Soviet Union in the 1950s, he told Soviet students: "The world belongs to you, and also to us, but ultimately it belongs to you. You young people, full of vigor, are in your prime, like the sun at eight or nine in the morning, hope rests on you". Deng Xiaoping earnestly pointed out that "the growth of the young generation is precisely where our cause's inevitable prosperity lies", hoping young people would strive to become new people with four qualities. Jiang Zemin emphasized that "when youth prosper, the nation prospers; when youth are strong, the nation is strong", hoping young people would persevere and pioneer for the Party and people's cause. Hu Jintao pointed out, "Highly value youth moral education, cultivate civilized customs". Xi Jinping pointed out, "Young people should bravely shoulder the responsibilities endowed by the times, aim high while keeping feet on the ground, and strive to realize their youth dreams in the vivid practice of achieving the Chinese nation's great rejuvenation dream".

University students are the nation's future, bearing the historical responsibility of building socialist modernization with Chinese characteristics, representing the hope of the country and nation, and are the backbone force of social development. Their ideological and moral qualities directly affect the smooth progress of socialism with Chinese characteristics. The university period is also a time of dramatic physiological and psychological changes, and a critical period for forming correct worldviews, life outlooks, and values, with great plasticity. Strengthening university students' ideological and political education is an important content of current university education.

3 Dilemmas in the Application of Red Resources in University Students' Ideological and Political Education

3.1 The Uniqueness of Red Resources

Red resources have become valuable ideological and political educational resources in the new era due to their noble spiritual connotations, scientific theoretical qualities, and the historical conditions and temporal background of their formation, inherently belonging to the ideological and political education system. They present unique characteristics: historical longevity in time, scattered distribution in space, and latent values. These unique characteristics create certain temporal, spatial, theoretical, and psychological distances between red resources and the university student population.

First, the temporal gap. Most parts of red resources with strong educational functions were formed during the New Democratic Revolution, socialist transformation and construction period, and the early stages of reform and opening up, relatively distant from modern life, creating a gap with today's social reality. For example, the Long March spirit, reflecting the Red Army officers' and soldiers' absolute loyalty to revolutionary ideals and causes, firm beliefs, fearlessness of sacrifice, courage to win, and proletarian optimism, along with their noble qualities of considering the overall situation, strictly observing discipline, and maintaining close unity, has over 70 years of history. For the older generation who lived through the revolutionary war and construction era, red resources are particularly familiar. For the middle-aged who experienced the nation's economic near-collapse, poverty, and tortuous development of socialist construction, they often harbor deep feelings for red resources. However, for the younger and middle generations born after reform and opening up, especially contemporary university students, material abundance and superior living conditions undoubtedly make them lack firsthand experience of their predecessors' struggles, feeling unfamiliar with red resources. This is also why some people propose erroneous views like "red culture obsolescence theory" and "red resources uselessness theory". We need to strengthen the younger generation's understanding of Chinese Communist Party history and military history through various means, eliminate temporal barriers by transforming red resources with contemporary relevance, turning them into quality modern educational resources.

Second, the spatial gap. During the anti-Japanese war era, China's special national conditions forced the revolution to take a unique path of rural areas encircling cities. The Chinese people's blood-stained struggle footprints spread throughout China; during the socialist construction period, distinctive spirits of arduous struggle and selfless dedication ignited the passion of builders across China. Revolutionary sites, glorious deeds, and other red resources are often distributed in remote areas, too numerous to count. These places are mostly located in remote mountainous areas at the junction of several provinces, with inconvenient transportation, creating a spatial distance from university students who study and live in convenient cities.

Third, the theoretical gap. Red resources include Mao Zedong Thought's New Democratic Revolution theory, socialist transformation theory, and the theoretical system of socialism with Chinese characteristics. Although these theories are not as abstruse as the theoretical works of Marx, Engels, and Lenin, they still possess certain abstractness. For contemporary university students, there is some difficulty in thoroughly mastering and applying Marxist positions, viewpoints, and methods to specific practical life and study through theoretical learning.

Fourth, the psychological gap. Red resources embody firm ideals and beliefs, profound advanced culture, rich revolutionary spirit, and noble personality charm, often carrying sublime coloring and strong political overtones. For university students accustomed to consuming grassroots culture, fast food culture, and Western culture, they may experience a certain psychological distance when receiving red resource education. University students' emotional and psychological alienation inevitably leads them to maintain a respectful but distant psychological attitude toward accepting red resources.

The uniqueness of red resources and their temporal, spatial, theoretical, and psychological gaps with university students undoubtedly build an invisible wall, causing difficulties in applying red resources in university students' ideological and political education.

3.2 New Characteristics of Contemporary University Students

Times are changing. Economic globalization, social informatization, system marketization, cultural diversification, and political multi-polarization intertwine, leaving deep imprints on university students and giving their thought activities distinct characteristics. First, enhanced independence. Unlike the planned economy era, contemporary university students grow up in a pluralistic society, with active thinking and distinctive personalities, quickly responding to new things, thoughts, and viewpoints in social life, with critical spirit and innovative consciousness. When observing and handling problems, they tend toward independent thinking and self-decision-making, showing stronger autonomy. Second, enhanced selectivity. Growing up in an open and diverse environment, university students constantly face various judgments and choices in their studies, friendships, and job searches. Facing the collision of different social thoughts and the interplay of different values, their ability to discriminate, analyze, and choose continuously strengthens. Third, variable thinking. Forming scientific worldviews, life outlooks, values, and establishing lofty ideals and beliefs requires a process of tempering. University students are in a life development stage of variable thinking, particularly prone to showing characteristics of multiplicity and variability in their value concepts.

3) Complexity of Educational Environment

Under social information technology conditions, changing international situations, Western cultural infiltration, and various negative phenomena appearing in the process of domestic system transformation and improvement intertwine, jointly affecting the realistic situation of contemporary university students' ideological and political education. As university students have more opportunities to contact different cultures and ideological consciousness, facing vast and

mixed information, some inexperienced or weak-willed university students often feel confused under its influence. Due to lack of analysis, discrimination, and resistance abilities, they may waver in their faith in Marxism and ideals of socialism with Chinese characteristics and communism.

Against the backdrop of system marketization, the weaknesses of market economy's spontaneity, utilitarianism, and blindness force university students to frequently face some recurring, hard-to-end value conflicts, inducing varying degrees of money worship, hedonism, and egoism tendencies among some university students. Phenomena occasionally appear such as emphasizing personal interests while neglecting social responsibility, focusing on material enjoyment while ignoring spiritual pursuit, stressing realistic experience while disregarding long-term responsibility, and advocating personal liberation while disregarding social norms.

Under the interplay of various types of ideological cultures, university students' thoughts continuously face impact. Western developed countries, relying on strong economic strength and advanced science and technology, firmly control cultural exchange information sources, dominate information flow direction, control information quantity and flow speed, and even cultural information nature, seriously impacting our country's mainstream position dominated by red culture and challenging contemporary university students' values.

4. Paths in the Application of Red Resources in University Students' Ideological and Political Education

4.1 Grasp University Students' Psychological Development Characteristics and Follow Their Acceptance Psychological Laws

University students' ideological and political education is a process of two-way interaction and mutual influence between university teachers and students. In other words, on one hand, it requires university teachers to conduct ideological and political education according to teaching objectives, adopting certain teaching methods and approaches; on the other hand, it also requires students to actively learn and acquire educational values through teachers' leading teaching, bringing their subject role into play according to social development requirements and their own development needs, actively internalizing it into their moral character and externalizing it into behavioral expression. Thus, as leading educators, teachers must adapt to students' acceptance psychology during education for it to be effective; meanwhile, teachers cannot merely passively adapt to students' acceptance psychology but should actively adjust and transcend it to achieve ideological and political education purposes (Hu, 2009).

Generally, red resources do not possess the direct practical value that people usually think, while bearing distinct class nature and strong political color. When university students accept red resource educational content, they often rely on people's existing ideological concepts, moral schemas, and demand choices. Compared to natural science knowledge and technical skills that show immediate effects and can produce economic benefits relatively quickly, its acceptance has greater difficulty. This requires university teachers to actively integrate red resources from students' needs perspective, using certain educational methods and means to stimulate students' learning enthusiasm. Meanwhile, they should actively guide students to correctly interpret red resources and actively accept red resource ideological and political education.

4.2 Grasp Era Characteristics, Enhance Educational Effectiveness of Red Resources in University Students' Ideological and Political Education Application

In today's era, the network world is an important place besides university students' real learning and life scenarios, necessarily becoming an important carrier for us to use red resources for ideological and political education. Grasping network ideological and political education characteristics such as resource intensification, education information vividness, education environment virtualization, education activity autonomy, and education time randomness can enhance education scientificity. Developing rich and diverse red resource network education can meet different psychological needs of university students, achieving targeted results. For example, some university students like red movies and TV dramas, some like red classic songs, some like calligraphy, painting, poetry and prose works. We can collect and organize works from different periods of revolution, construction, and reform for display, making university students' cognition of predecessors' revolutionary careers three-dimensional.

4.3 Strengthen Campus Red Culture Construction

"One takes on the color of one's company". Our growth cannot be separated from environmental influences. People will be elevated in beautiful, healthy, positive, and upward environments, with souls purified. That is to say, the campus culture where university students live daily imperceptibly influences their behavior, ideological concepts, and value orientations. Campus culture construction must occupy the commanding heights with correct guiding ideology, scientific theory, correct public opinion, and noble spirit. Red resources containing advanced political concepts, scientific value concepts, noble moral sentiment, and glorious patriotic tradition should undoubtedly seize campus cultural positions, becoming the soul of campus culture construction. Red resources interact with and depend on current campus red culture

construction with their unique spiritual connotations and innate educational functions, becoming the dominant force in campus culture construction.

Campus culture mainly includes material culture, spiritual culture, behavioral culture, and network culture. Material culture is an important carrier of campus culture. In campus culture construction, distinctive red landscapes with era characteristics should be "replicated" into campuses combined with regional features, such as architecture, sculpture, copying and other forms of modern art, creating intuitive environmental guidance and promoting teachers and students to form correct psychological behavior. Among these campus culture components, spiritual culture should be at the core position of campus culture, silently influencing and helping teachers and students establish correct life outlooks and values, maintain noble ideals and beliefs, achieving subtle effects, while also playing a guiding role in other aspects of campus culture construction. Behavioral culture is both the external manifestation of campus culture and conversely deepens campus culture's nurturing and recognition of teachers and students, enhancing campus culture's attraction and influence. Network culture, as a new field of campus culture, expands campus culture's development space, greatly enriching and developing campus culture's expression forms.

Therefore, doing well in campus red culture construction must innovate and plan campus red culture construction. Create a strong red humanistic atmosphere, influencing university students with excellent revolutionary traditions, affecting them with lofty revolutionary spirit, inspiring them with tragic revolutionary stories. Carry out Learn from Lei Feng activities, teaching support activities, three rural areas volunteer activities, and environmental protection activities on and off campus, implementing red resources' influence in university students' study and life practice. With the development of the times, contemporary university students have become the subject of network culture. We should value network campus red culture construction and fully utilize networks as carriers for campus red culture construction and dissemination. For university ideological and political education, campus network information environment has become a new educational environment. Educators must firmly grasp this new information environment's key elements and their acting relationships, organically unifying regularity and purposiveness to achieve network ideological and political education mode development and innovation (Hu & Feng, 2016).

4.4 Guide University Students' Rational Patriotism

Throughout history, university students have always been the vanguard and main force of patriotic movements, and many of their patriotic actions have promoted social progress and national rejuvenation. The main force of the May Fourth Movement was university students. Their patriotic spirit of not fearing power and fighting for truth and justice when facing major events concerning national sovereignty, core interests, and national dignity is worth learning for contemporary university students. Contemporary university students should not only have deep emotional feelings for the motherland but also have profound and comprehensive understanding of patriotism based on calm and rational grasp of their country's future and destiny; they should also learn to rationally express their patriotic appeals in action, consciously maintaining the overall situation of national and people's interests and social development stability as priority.

Red resources themselves are precious wealth collectively created by the Chinese Communist Party and the Chinese people under its leadership during long-term revolution, construction, and reform under patriotic calling. The red spirit it nurtures has always been a heightened patriotic spirit. The process of applying red resources to university students' ideological and political education points out the direction for our university students to reasonably and legally express strong patriotic emotions. We should guide university students to be rational and practical in patriotism. Ideologically, through the most convincing textbooks, guide university students to consciously understand that loving the country is consistent with loving the Party and loving socialism, and recognize that our Party's leadership and the country's socialist development path are choices of history and the people. Without the Chinese Communist Party, there would be no national independence and people's liberation; without socialism, there would be no national prosperity and people's wealth. In action, actively guide university students to be rational and practical in patriotism, expressing patriotic emotions reasonably, rationally, and legally. The proposal of rational patriotism is an objective requirement of era development. This requires contemporary university students to start from the trend of peace and development when expressing patriotic emotions, toward the goal of seeking new development in the important strategic opportunity period of the new era, consciously maintaining the hard-won stability of national interests and socialist China, remembering that practical work builds the nation.

5. Conclusion

Red resources, as carriers of the Chinese Communist Party's great practical experience and national spirit, contain rich ideological educational value and hold significant importance for cultivating new-era university students' ideological and moral character. In university ideological and political education, how to scientifically and rationally transform red resources into educational resources that are easily accepted and have practical value has become a core task. Through deep exploration of red resources' connotations, universities can extract their ideological essence, combine scientific

educational methods, and better serve university students' ideological and political education, helping them strengthen ideals and beliefs and shape correct value concepts.

However, the application of red resources also faces many challenges, which is both a test of the university education system and an opportunity to promote educational innovation. Temporal, spatial, theoretical, and psychological gaps create a sense of distance between red resources and university students, weakening their educational effectiveness. Meanwhile, university students' independent, diverse, and critical thinking characteristics, along with value changes brought by cultural impacts in the network information age, further increase the complexity of integrating red resources into the educational process. University ideological and political education needs to take active countermeasures, shortening the distance between red resources and university students through innovative educational methods, optimized resource integration, and diversified dissemination forms, stimulating the vitality of their ideological and political education from multiple aspects.

Enhancing the effectiveness of red resources in ideological and political education requires seizing contemporary opportunities, especially using digital network technology to create educational carriers and platforms that meet university students' needs. For example, combining red resources with film and television, music, literature, and network culture can effectively improve the attractiveness of educational content. Meanwhile, promoting campus red culture construction integrates red resources' spiritual connotations into daily life, allowing university students to internalize them into their own ideological concepts and behavioral norms through subtle influence. Through diverse red cultural practice activities such as volunteer service, social practice, and themed education, educators can help university students deeply perceive red resources' contemporary value. Ultimately, universities should comprehensively promote the application of red resources in ideological and political education through scientific planning and innovative methods, providing important ideological guarantee for cultivating successors and builders of the socialist cause with Chinese characteristics in the new era.

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